

Hyperpigmented Macular Rash on the Lower Extremities

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ABSTRACT

Drug induced hyperpigmentation is a rare cause of acquired hyperpigmentation and represents about 10-20 % of the cases. The predisposing factor is most commonly a non-specific cutaneous inflammation resulting in accumulation of melanin which is often worsened by exposure to sun. Treatment is limited to avoiding the triggering agents and avoiding sun exposure. We present a case of Minocycline induced hyperpigmentation in an area without any prior cutaneous inflammation.

Key words: Hyperpigmentation; Reaction, Side-effect; Minocycline

CASE REPORT

A 62-year-old woman presented with rash on her left lower extremity that has been progressively darkening for the last five months. She does not have any discoloration of eyes (sclera or conjunctiva), ears, gums, and teeth. She has a medical history significant for pulmonary embolism which was provoked secondary to prolonged immobility after a left total knee arthroplasty and well controlled diabetes mellitus. The patient's total knee arthroplasty was complicated by septic arthritis for which she has been on chronic minocycline for suppression. The patient did not have any history of any systemic symptoms like fever or weight loss. Physical exam is pertinent for dermal hyperpigmented macules (Figures 1 and 2). They are only located on the distal aspect of her left lower extremity. There is no evidence of rash anywhere else on the body. There is no evidence of any murmur on exam. The surgical scar has healed well.

Figure 1: Dermal Hyper Pigmented Macule

Figure 2: Dermal Hyper Pigmented Macule on left lower extremity

The differential diagnosis includes-

1. Post inflammatory hyperpigmentation
2. Drug induced hyperpigmentation
3. Addisons disease
4. Idiopathic eruptive macular pigmentation (IEMP)

DIAGNOSIS

The patient has drug-induced hyperpigmentation from her chronic use of minocycline. What makes this case unusual is the distribution not only on her anterior distal lower extremity but also on the dorsal aspect of her toes, not at an area of previous inflammation, such as her scar from knee replacement.

Cutaneous hyperpigmentation is usually due to increased melanin synthesis and/or deposition of the drug or its products in the dermis^[1]. The most common pigmentation reaction to minocycline is a blue-black discoloration in areas of previous inflammation, such as with acne or surgical scars. It typically takes at least three months of continuous minocycline usage before this type of reaction presents^[2].

The incidence of drug-induced pigmentation is around 10-20% of all cases of acquired pigmentation^[3]. On histologic examination, there is evidence of pigmented granules within macrophages predominantly in the dermis. It is common that the granules will stain positive for both iron and melanin.

The diagnosis of drug induced hyperpigmentation is mainly clinical with a relevant history. Biopsy can confirm the diagnosis in doubtful cases.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Post inflammatory hyperpigmentation typically occurs with any inflammatory skin conditions like acne vulgaris or atopic dermatitis. This patient did not have any predisposing inflammatory conditions which would cause her to have post inflammatory hyperpigmentation.

Cutaneous manifestations of Addison's disease include generalized hyperpigmentation of the skin and mucous membranes. Oral mucosal hyperpigmentation is pathognomonic for Addison's. There are also systemic symptoms of fatigue, weight loss and low blood pressures associated with Addison's disease.

Idiopathic eruptive macular pigmentation (IEMP) occurs sporadically in the absence of preceding illness, inflammation, sun exposure or medications.

MANAGEMENT

The mainstays of treatment for drug-induced hyperpigmentation have historically been sun avoidance and replacing the drug that is suspected of eliciting the reaction. There have been recent investigations into the use of laser therapy for some cases^[4].

Our patient has been advised to discontinue the minocycline and start Cephalexin for MSSA prophylaxis. The patient was advised on the importance of wearing sunscreen and UV protective clothing. The goal of discontinuing minocycline is to prevent the current lesions from darkening and new ones from developing. The hope is that over time, the current lesions lessen in severity, eventually resolving. Should the patient require further treatment for her drug-induced hyperpigmentation, next steps include cosmetic camouflage and other pigment-reducing

treatments such as laser therapy^[5]. Treating hyperpigmentation disorders can be challenging as they are often resistant to treatment and tend to recur after completion of treatment. There is also a risk of worsening the hyperpigmentation while trying to treat the patient^[6].

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